

Intestinal Mal-Rotation in an Adult Male: Case Report and Literature Review**Author Details:**

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Introduction: *intestinal mal-rotation is widely considered pediatric pathology where the vast majority of presentation would occur. In the pediatric population, this condition has an incidence rate of about 1 in 500 live births⁽⁷⁾ in which 75% to 85% of these are diagnosed in infancy. An adult population presentation is an increasing form in which in several studies conducted by Nehra et al., and Kotobi et al., and have shown prevalence rates of 48%⁽¹⁾ and 42%⁽²⁾ respectively. Although according to other studies the true incidence in the adult population is difficult to calculate⁽²³⁾. This is partially due to the fact that a significant proportion may remain asymptomatic throughout their lives⁽²⁴⁾ and the rest are diagnosed intra-operatively during other procedures or at autopsy⁽²⁵⁾.*

Method: *This case of a 36-year-old male patient well-nourished and average height was hospitalized with a presenting complaint of abdominal pain for one day. This patient had a Past medical history of asthma with the last attack a week prior to this presentation. On physical examination was found to be afebrile and hemodynamically stable. The abdominal findings were distension and generalized tenderness. There were no mass or organomegaly on palpation. However, there was a brown stool and scant blood on digital rectal examination. A nasogastric tube was sited. The urinary catheter was not cited as this patient had urethral strictures. Strict input and out charting were done along with appropriate monitoring of vital signs. The laboratory investigations were found to be within normal range. The abdominal radiographic findings were multiple air-fluid levels on erect view and dilated loops of bowel on the horizontal view.*

Results: *This patient was resuscitated with intravenous fluid therapy, analgesia, prophylactic antibiotic along with deep vein thrombosis prophylaxis and booked for exploratory laparotomy. Intra-operatively Ladd's bands with a mal-rotated intestine were found. Ladd's procedure and supra-pubic cystostomy were done. The patient had an uneventful postoperative period and was discharged home on day 5th post-op with regular surgical outpatient follow up.*

Conclusion: *This late presentation of a congenital pathology such as intestinal mal-rotation can be a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge. Therefore the need to include this as an armament in the diagnostic differentials in an adult with a vague abdominal complaint is essential to avoid any surgical catastrophe. The Ladd's procedure is the current gold standard.*

Keywords: *Mal-rotation, Intestinal volvulus, Ladd's procedure.*

Introduction

Intestinal Mal-rotation encompasses varying degree of a part to a complete lack of 270 degrees counter-clockwise rotation of the mid-gut structure around the mesentery. This intrauterine process usually occurs around the tenth to twelve-week fetal development. This developmental anomaly produces a narrow-based mesentery, which increases the risk of mid-gut volvulus and subsequent vascular compromise. The pediatric presentation is seen in mainly in the first month of life with bile stained vomitus and abdominal distension.

The presentation of intestinal mal-rotation in adults is rare, and occurs in approximately 0.2%⁽¹⁰⁾ of all the case reported which was further corroborated by other studies of adult intestinal mal-rotation with an incidence reported to be between 0.0001% and 0.19%^(3, 4) of that population. In general, most adults affected are asymptomatic and may have chronic symptoms such as vague abdominal pain, distension, dyspepsia, and constipation can occur in some cases.

The adult population presentation has been shown in several studies conducted by Nehra et al., and Kotobi et al., to have and prevalence rates of 48%⁽¹⁾ and 42%⁽²⁾ respectively. This suggests that there may be a significant adult population who have been asymptomatic or have non-urgent chronic abdominal complaints. There is a small proportion of affected adult who may present with acute or chronic symptoms of intestinal

obstruction with intermittent and recurrent abdominal pain. The correct diagnosis in this age group is fraught with immense difficulty, mainly because the typical presentation is with non-specific symptoms.

This case report is based on an adult male patient who presented with intestinal mal-rotation which demonstrates the difficulty in an accurate preoperative diagnosis, which corroborated by our literature review.

Case Report

This is a 36-year-old male patient, who is clinically well nourished, who presented to the accident and emergency department with peri-umbilical pain for one day. This pain was colicky in nature and had radiated to the lower abdomen and back with an intensity of 10/10, no diarrhea or vomiting, with nil aggravating or relieving factors. The patient had no known surgical history and with a past medical history of asthma with the last attack being a week prior to presentation. On physical examination, the patient was afebrile and hemodynamically stable. The abdominal findings were nil surgical scars, asymmetrical distension and generalized tenderness with voluntary guarding. There were no masses or organomegaly on palpation. However, there was a brown stool and scant blood on digital rectal examination. The routine laboratory results for complete blood count, amylase and u/e (urea and electrolyte) were within normal range. The abdominal radiographic findings (fig. 3) were multiple air-fluid levels on erect view and dilated loops of bowel on the horizontal view (fig. 2). In retrospect, the chest radiograph also demonstrated dilated loops of large bowel (fig. 1).

Radiographic images

Figure 1. Demonstrating an erect chest radiograph with dilated loops of bowel (shown with arrow) in the left upper quadrant of the intestine.

Figure 2. demonstrating a supine abdominal radiograph with dilated loops of large bowel (shown with red arrow) in upper quadrant and dilated loops of bowel (shown with yellow arrow) in the lower quadrants.

Figure 3. demonstrating an erect abdominal radiograph with dilated loops of large bowel (shown with yellow arrow) in the left upper quadrant and air-fluid levels of the small bowel (shown with red arrow) in the lower quadrant.

This patient was subsequently diagnosed with an acute abdomen (hence the preoperative diagnostic dilemma) secondary to a possible ruptured appendix. This patient was resuscitated with intravenous fluid therapy, analgesia, prophylactic antibiotic and booked for exploratory laparotomy. The intraoperative findings were;

There were dilated loops of small bowel (image 2), which were located to the right of the abdominal cavity. There was an identified point of volvulus of the small bowel (image 1), with a shortened mesentery which had no vascular compromise. The general orientation of the intestine demonstrated that the small bowel was on the right side of the abdominal cavity with a straight duodenum (lack of loop) which followed with the duodenum- jejunum flexure (midline not crossed) and caecum in the midline.

The characteristic Ladd's band extending from the right lateral abdominal wall and the lower border of the liver, through to the caecum and the ascending colon to the second part of the duodenum were identified.

Intraoperative images

Image 1. Demonstrating small bowel volvulus with a shortened mesentery.

Image 2. Demonstrating small bowel (shown with black arrow) and large bowel (shown with yellow arrow) dilatation.

The Ladd's Procedure was performed where the Ladd's bands were excised hence releasing the small bowel. The small bowel mesenteric base was widened carefully so as to avoid any vascular compromise. The appendectomy was done to prevent future diagnostic confusion. The small bowel was placed on the right side of the abdominal cavity, and large bowel kept on the left side with the caecum essentially abutting the midline.

The patient had an uneventful postoperative recovery and was discharged home on the fifth-day post-surgery. On follow up he was well, and there had been no late complications.

Discussion

The adult presentation of intestinal mal-rotation is rare as this is mainly thought to be a pediatric pathology. However, the prevalence is increasing as a significant number of cases remain quiescent during childhood^(1, 2). The incidence of intestinal mal-rotation in the adult population remains at a constant 0.2%^(3, 4, 10). However, evidence from postmortem studies suggests that intestinal mal-rotation may affect as many as 1 in 6000⁽⁵⁾ adults.

The sequence of events for intestinal mal-rotation was outlined by Dott in 1923⁽²⁹⁾ and subsequently by Kiesewetter in 1958⁽³⁰⁾ where the normal 270 degrees counter-clockwise rotation of the gut during embryonic development is not achieved. The foregut, midgut and hindgut development is essentially based on the anatomical blood supply, which during the 4th week of fetal development will cause the primitive embryonic gut to develop these respective vascular pedicles. The superior mesenteric artery (SMA) which supplies the mid-gut would have both (gut and vessel) initiated by the fifth week of embryonic life several sequential processes of rapid prolongation⁽²⁸⁾.

This rapid growth would subsequently provoke a herniation of the primitive intestine into the umbilical cord, which by the sixth week of fetal life this is an established norm that allows further development of the intestine. The subsequent return of the intestine to the abdominal cavity about 4 to 6 weeks later has to be orchestrated in such a way to allow for all rotation peritoneal and retroperitoneal structures⁽²⁸⁾. The midgut which entails the duodenum, jejunum, ileum, caecum, ascending colon and 2/3 proximal transverse colon undergoes a 270 degree counter-clockwise rotation around the SMA axis. This process leads to the formation of the duodenal C-loop around the head of the pancreas (retroperitoneal structure), placing it behind the SMA in a retroperitoneal position and emerging at the ligament of Treitz on the left of the midline as the duodenojejunal flexure⁽²⁸⁾.

In essence, the physiological midgut herniation commences to progressively return to the abdominal cavity at around week 10 of embryonic life. The coordinated sequence of reduction is as follows, the duodenojejunal flexure (DJF) and jejunum are to reduce first and lie to the left. The distal small bowel (ileum) then follows and lies progressively to the right lower quadrant of the abdominal cavity. The ultimate descent of the caecum from its higher position in the right upper quadrant to the lower quadrant forms the

latter part of this complex rotational development; it becomes positioned in the right lower abdomen as it affixed by a shortened mesentery. The ascending colon then assumes a retroperitoneal position, also on the right side. The base of the small bowel mesentery subsequently fuses with the posterior peritoneum in a diagonal fashion, from the ligament of Treitz at the DJF to the caecum, completing the whole process at about the eleventh week of fetal development ^(6,7).

The failure of this process leads to various degrees of anomaly including the entire small bowel remaining on the right side of the abdomen, the caecum, appendix and colon on the left and an absent ligament of Treitz. Additionally, the small bowel mesentery may develop a narrow vertical attachment and the peritoneal fibrous bands fixing the duodenum and caecum to the abdominal wall essentially the basis of Ladd's bands.

These congenital bands extend from the right lateral abdominal wall, across the duodenum and attach to the undescended caecum and are known as Ladd's bands ^(8,9). Ladd's bands compress the duodenum and can potentially cause duodenal obstruction. The mal-rotation of the gut and abnormal location of the caecum produces a narrow superior mesenteric vascular pedicle, as opposed to the normally broad-based small bowel mesentery. This narrow SMA take-off and lack of posterior peritoneal fusion predispose to subsequent midgut volvulus and obstruction with potential vascular catastrophe ⁽¹⁰⁾.

There are two distinct patterns of adult presentations have been reported in the literature: acute and chronic ^(5,8,11), with the latter being the most frequent. This is characterized by intermittent crampy abdominal pain, bloating, nausea and vomiting over several months or years. This vague presentation of clinical symptomatology underlines the need for a high index of suspicion of midgut mal-rotation in the young healthy adults.

In the acute presentation, the adults will typically present with symptoms of acute abdomen with varying etiology such inflammatory, obstructive, perforative and or a mixture and these patients may or may not report a previous history of abdominal symptoms, as with this patient. The acute presentation may be due to volvulus of the mid-gut or ileo-caecum, reported as the most common cause of bowel obstruction in adults with intestinal mal-rotation ⁽²⁸⁾, a significant cause of acute presentation may be related to internal herniation caused by Ladd's bands ⁽²⁸⁾. There is also a subgroup of these patients who present for other common abdominal diseases. Their unusual intestinal anatomy results in atypical signs and symptoms. These patients may present with localized peritonitis in the right upper quadrant or on the left side of the abdomen if their appendix becomes inflamed. The atypical presentations may lead to confusion, as one of the common abdominal pathologies may mimic another, leading to an incorrect diagnosis of conditions such as acute appendicitis, cholecystitis, and pancreatitis, perforated peptic ulcer disease and left colonic diverticulitis.

Diagnostic features of midgut mal-rotation can be identified using plain abdominal radiograph, ultrasound scan (USS), computed tomography (CT) scan, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scan and mesenteric arteriography ⁽¹²⁾. The plain radiography is neither sensitive nor specific in the diagnosis of gut mal-rotation, abdominal color Doppler USS may reveal malposition of the SMA, raising the suspicion of intestinal mal-rotation with or without the abnormal location of the hollow viscous ⁽¹²⁾. The USS findings of midgut volvulus were first described by Pacers et al. and these findings include duodenal dilatation with distal tapering and fixed midline bowel and mesentery twisted around the SMA axis. These features classically present as the "whirlpool" sign ⁽¹³⁾.

The reported gold standard for diagnosis of gut mal-rotation is an upper gastrointestinal (UGI) contrast study, particularly in the pediatric age group, ^(5,12,13). This will generally show the duodenum and duodenojejunal flexure located to the right of the spine.

CT scan with or without UGI contrast study is increasingly used preferentially as it is now considered as the investigation of choice; providing diagnostic accuracy of 80% ^(5,12,13). The position of the superior mesenteric vein (SMV) in relation to the superior mesenteric artery (SMA) is one diagnostic tool used in studies such as CT and MRI hence if the SMV is posterior or to the left is of diagnostic value. This anomaly

was originally described by Nichols and Li as a useful indicator of the diagnosis of intestinal mal-rotation⁽¹⁴⁾.

The CT appearance of midgut volvulus is diagnostic of intestinal mal-rotation; The shortened mesentery allows the small bowel and mesentery to twist and wrap around the narrowed SMA pedicle to create a distinctive “whirlpool” appearance on CT scan. This pattern was first described by Fisher in a patient with midgut volvulus⁽¹⁵⁾. The CT scan findings of gut mal-rotation and small bowel obstruction without volvulus may show internal herniation secondary to Ladd’s bands.

The angiographic study has been essentially replaced by the more detailed CT scan however the angiography was used to demonstrate the characteristic corkscrew appearance of a whirling SMA and its branches; the ‘barber pole sign’ as well as extensive collaterals caused by proximal SMA occlusion⁽¹⁶⁾.

The surgical management of intestinal mal-rotation was first described by William Ladd in 1936, and this remains the mainstay of treatment⁽⁶⁾, which essentially consist of 4 parts; division of Ladd’s bands overlying the duodenum; widening of the narrowed root of the small bowel mesentery by mobilizing the duodenum and division of the adhesions around the SMA to prevent further volvulus; counter-clockwise detorsioning of the midgut volvulus if present and appendectomy to prevent future diagnostic dilemma of an abnormally located appendix^(6,17).

These principles have remained the same since Ladd’s address to the New Hampshire Medical Society in 1936⁽⁶⁾. Generally, symptomatic patients with intestinal mal-rotation should be treated surgically. Moreover, Spigland et al., recommended that all patients with intestinal mal-rotation are candidates for laparotomy, even if they are asymptomatic, because the complications associated with intestinal mal-rotation are based on anatomical reasons that do not alter with age, thus the potential to develop sudden onset of acute midgut volvulus in an asymptomatic patient, at any age, exists⁽²¹⁾.

There have been variations of the Ladd’s procedure used to manage intestinal mal-rotation to prevent recurrent volvulus. These include re-establishment of the normal gut anatomy by duodenotomy, cecopexy and suture fixation of the ascending colon to the right abdominal wall, in the retroperitoneal position^(4, 5, 18).

There are recent reports of the use of the laparoscopic approach in the surgical treatment of intestinal malrotation. The technique appears to be safe and effective when performed by experienced laparoscopic surgeons, especially in the absence of volvulus^(8, 9, 10, 18, 19). This approach is being considered as an adequate initial intervention in the pediatric population with only a few such cases being reported in the adult population. There is a considerable benefit to the laparoscopic Ladd’s procedure with a decreased hospital stay, decreased pain, less scar tissue, however, the technical challenge may increase the need for risk conversion to an open procedure^(8, 9, 10, 18, 19, 20, 22,).

The overall recurrence rate post-surgical intervention is based the pediatric population in which it is quoted as being between 2-7%^(26, 27). There is not enough published data on the adult presentation of intestinal mal-rotation post-surgical intervention to state a value for the recurrence rate in this population.

Conclusion

Intestinal mal-rotation in the adult population is a rare presentation of a congenital pathology. The vagueness of the presenting symptoms has led to the diagnostic dilemma and subsequent treatment delay with possible bowel ischemia and necrosis in persons with the chronic intestinal complaint. Therefore a high index of suspicion has to be maintained in this subset of the patient which should prompt the appropriate contrast radiological investigation and eventually lead to an urgent surgical management. The surgical intervention of choice is the Ladd’s procedure whether in its standard form or the varying modifications, which has demonstrated according to many kinds of literature a low recurrence.

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